

Development of ion-association methods for the spectrophotometric assay of trazodone

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Simple and sensitive spectrophotometric methods (M_1 – M_3) for the assay of trazodone (TZ) are proposed. These methods are based on the formation of ion-association complex involving tertiary nitrogen of TZ and the acidic dye, supracene violet 3B (SV 3B) (M_1), tropaeolin 000 (TP 000) (M_2) or wool fast blue BL (WFB BL) (M_3). Beer's law and precision and accuracy of the methods are checked. The methods are suitable for the assay of trazodone in pharmaceutical formulations, and the recovery range is 99.17–99.16%.

Trazodone¹ (as hydrochloride) is an antidepressant with little antimuscarinic activity but marked sedative properties. It is chemically known as 1,2,4-triazolo[4,3-*a*]pyridin-3(2*H*)-one, 2-[3-[4-(3-chlorophenyl)-1-piperazinyl]propyl]-, monohydrochloride]. There are several analytical methods for the assay of TZ². During the course of our efforts to develop sensitive visible spectrophotometric methods, it was observed that the analytically useful tertiary amino group in TZ has not been properly exploited. Hence, there is a need to develop some new methods with either sensitivity or selectivity by exploiting the tertiary amino group in TZ. As the

extraction spectrophotometric procedures are popular for their sensitivity and selectivity in the determination of drugs, the technique was therefore utilized in the present work for the assay of TZ. TZ being basic in nature forms an ion-association complex with the acidic dye, namely, SV 3B³, TP 000⁴ or WFB BL³, which is extractable into chloroform. The protonated aliphatic tertiary nitrogen (positive charge) of the TZ in acid medium is expected to attract the oppositely charged part (negative charge) of the dye (SO_3^-) and behave as a single unit being held together by electrostatic attraction (Scheme 1). The results are statistically validated.

Scheme 1. Ion association complexes of TZ with SV 3B, TP 000 and WFB BL.

Results and Discussion

Optimum conditions fixation :

The optimum conditions for the color development of the methods were established by varying the parameters one at a time keeping the others fixed and observing the effect produced on the absorbance of the colored species⁵. The following experiments were conducted for this purpose and the conditions so obtained were incorporated in the recommended procedure. In the preliminary investigations, nine acidic dyes belonging to different chemical categories with pH ranges or volumes of 0.1 M HCl were tested. The comparative $\lambda_{\max}$ and $\epsilon_{\max}$ values of the nine acidic dyes tested with TZ are presented in Table 1. Since SV 3B, TP 000 and WFB BL produced high molar absorptivity values, they were selected for further investigations. The effect of pH (or acidity) was studied by extracting the colored complex formed in the presence of various acidic buffers (or volumes of HCl).

Table 1. $\lambda_{\max}$ and $\epsilon_{\max}$ values of TZ-dye complexes

Sl. no.	Dye	Category	$\lambda_{\max}$ nm	$10^4 \epsilon_{\max}$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
1.	Tropaeolin 00	Azo dye	540	1.20
2.	Tropaeolin 000*	Azo dye	480	3.76
3.	Naphthol blue black	Azo dye	580	0.56
4.	Naphthalene blue 12 BR	Azo dye	620	0.79
5.	Azocarmine G	Phenazine dye	540	0.47
6.	Lissamine blue BF	Phenazine dye	560	0.13
7.	Wool fast blue BL*	Phenazine dye	580	4.94
8.	Alizarine Red S	Anthraquinone dye	435	1.15
9.	Supracen violet 3B*	Anthraquinone dye	560	2.41

*Chosen for further investigations.

Of the various buffers (or acids) tried, pH 1.3 buffer, 0.1 M HCl and pH 1.5 buffer were found to be more suitable for methods M₁, M₂ and M₃, respectively. Six ml of buffer or acid was found to be optimal. Decrease in absorbance of the complex was observed when either the pH values or volumes of buffer (or acid) was decreased. The optimum volume of the dye used was also studied. Optimization experiments revealed that an increase in absorbance reading with the increase of the volume of dye upto 2.0 ml (4.63×10^{-3} M SV 3B for M₁, 5.70×10^{-3} M TP 000 for M₂ or 3.26×10^{-3} M WFB BL for M₃). However, a significant increase in the absorbance value of the blank (more than 0.05 absorbance unit) was observed at volumes larger than 2.0 ml. From the organic solvents tested (benzene, toluene, nitrobenzene, carbon tetrachloride, 1,2-dichloromethane and chloroform), the chloroform was found to be most suitable

Table 2. Optical characteristics, precision and accuracy of the proposed methods for TZ

Parameter	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃
$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	560	480	580
Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	2-10	1-6	1-5
Detection limit ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.054	0.066	0.101
Molar absorptivity (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	2.41×10^4	3.76×10^4	4.94×10^4
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}/0.001$ absorbance unit)	0.016	0.010	0.008
Optimum photometric range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	3.2-8.4	1.8-5.2	1.3-4.2
Regression equation (y) ^a			
Slope (b)	5.87×10^{-2}	9.16×10^{-2}	1.16×10^{-1}
Intercept (a)	3.00×10^{-3}	1.06×10^{-3}	1.10×10^{-3}
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9999	0.9999	0.9998
Relative standard deviation (%) ^b	0.575	0.401	0.557
% range of error (95% confidence limits)	0.603	0.421	0.585

^a $y = a + bc$, where c is the concentration in $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and y the absorbance unit.

^bSix replicate samples.

Table 3. Assay of TZ in pharmaceutical formulations

Pharmaceutical sample	% Recovery (mg)			Ref. method ^d
	Proposed method ^c			
(Labeled amount)	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	
T ₁ (50 mg) ^a	99.76 ± 0.43 $t = 1.08$ $F = 2.65$	99.80 ± 0.85 $t = 1.44$ $F = 1.47$	99.20 ± 0.88 $t = 0.62$ $F = 1.58$	99.51 ± 0.70
T ₂ (50 mg) ^b	99.17 ± 0.67 $t = 1.21$ $F = 1.32$	99.21 ± 0.51 $t = 1.22$ $F = 2.27$	99.28 ± 0.54 $t = 1.31$ $F = 2.03$	99.93 ± 0.77
T ₃ (100 mg) ^a	99.58 ± 0.71 $t = 1.21$ $F = 1.53$	99.81 ± 0.69 $t = 0.96$ $F = 1.62$	99.25 ± 0.65 $t = 0.75$ $F = 1.83$	99.48 ± 0.88
T ₄ (100 mg) ^b	99.91 ± 0.22 $t = 1.23$ $F = 2.53$	99.82 ± 0.56 $t = 0.89$ $F = 2.56$	99.96 ± 0.69 $t = 0.15$ $F = 3.88$	99.19 ± 0.35

^aCompany : Torrent (Ahmedabad). ^bCompany : Sun Pharma (Mumbai).

^cAverage ($\pm$ RSD) of six determinations; the t and F values refer to comparison of the proposed method with the reference method; theoretical values at 95% confidence limits, $t = 2.57$, $F = 5.05$. ^dRef. 1.

because of the lowest extractability of free dyes and ease of extractability of ion-associated in it. A ratio of 3 : 2 of aqueous to chloroform phases was required for efficient extrac-

tion of the colored species. Shaking times of 0.5–5.0 min produced a constant absorbance and hence a shaking time of 2 min was used throughout. The color products were stable upto 30 min. The stoichiometric ratio of the TZ to dye was found as 1 : 1 with SV 3B and TP 000 or 2 : 1 with WFB BL through slope analysis method.

Interference studies :

The effects of various substances that often accompany in various pharmaceutical formulations were studied. To an aliquot containing 60 μg of TZ, different amounts of various ingredients and additives were added individually until a solution showed the same absorbance (± 0.01) as that of pure TZ solution under experimental conditions as described under the procedure. The commonly used ingredients and additives in the preparation of formulation such as talc (upto 200-fold excess, w/v), starch (150-fold), boric acid (150-fold), stearic acid (70-fold), magnesium stearate (50-fold), kaolin (30-fold), sodium lauryl sulfate (10-fold) and gelatin (10-fold), did not interfere with the assay of TZ by proposed methods.

Analytical data :

The optical characteristics such as Beer's law limits, molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity for the method are given in Table 2. The precision of the method was found by measuring absorbances of six replicate samples containing known amounts of drug. Regression analysis using the method of least-squares was made to evaluate the parameters. The accuracy of the methods was ascertained by comparing the results by the reference method (UV)¹ (Table 3). This comparison shows that there is no significant difference between the results of studied methods and those of the reference one. Hence, all the proposed methods are simple and sensitive and useful for the assay of TZ in pure and pharmaceutical formulations.

Experimental

Milton Roy Spectronic 1201 and Systronics 106 digital spectrophotometers with 1 cm matched quartz cells were used. An Elico LI-120 pH meter was used.

All the reagents and chemicals used were of analytical or pharmacopoeial grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout. Aqueous solutions of SV 3B (Chroma, $4.63 \times 10^{-3} M$), TP 000 (Fluka, $5.70 \times 10^{-3} M$), WFB BL (Fluka, $3.26 \times 10^{-3} M$), glycine-HCl buffer solution (pH 1.3 for method M₁ and pH 1.5 for method M₃) and HCl solution (E. Merck, 0.1 M for method M₂) were prepared in double-distilled water. A 1 mg ml⁻¹ solution of pure trazodone (for bulk samples, Sun Pharma, Mumbai) or active ingredients (for tablets, Sun Pharma, Mumbai and Torrent, Ahmedabad)

was prepared in 0.01 N HCl and this stock solution was diluted further with 0.01 N HCl to obtain the working standard solutions of concentration of 20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

Procedure : To each of the aliquots of standard TZ solution (1.0–5.0 ml, 20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (M₁), 0.5–3.0 ml, 20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (M₂), 0.5–2.5 ml, 20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (M₃), the buffer solution (6.0 ml) (pH 1.3 (M₁) and pH 1.5 (M₃)) or 0.1 M HCl solution (M₂) and SV 3B (M₁), TP 000 (M₂) or WFB BL (M₃) solutions (2.0 ml) were added and the total volume of aqueous phase was adjusted to 15.0 ml with distilled water. Then chloroform (10 ml) was added to it and shaken for 2 min. The two phases were allowed to separate and the absorbance of the separated chloroform layer was measured at 560 nm (M₁), 480 nm (M₂) or 580 nm (M₃) against the reagent blank. The amount of TZ was calculated from the calibration plot.

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